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Toxic effects of cadmium on liver biomarkers in Wistar rats (*Rattus norvegicus*): protective effects of jamun (*Syzygium cumini*) seed and orange (*Citrus sinensis*) peel extracts

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ABSTRACT: The present study investigated the alternation in liver function parameters such as serum glutamic oxaloacetic transaminase (SGOT), serum glutamic pyruvic transaminase (SGPT), bilirubin (Bil), albumin (Alb), alkaline phosphatases (ALP) and lactate dehydrogenase (LDH) of cadmium exposed Wistar rats. The study also evaluated the possible ameliorative effects of jamun (*Syzygium cumini*) seed and orange (*Citrus sinensis*) peel extracts on liver biomarkers in rat treated with cadmium. Six groups of Wistar rats were treated as Group A: Control; Group B: cadmium (10 mg/kg b wt.); Group C: cadmium (10 mg/kg b wt.) and jamun seed extract (200mg/kg b wt.); Group D: cadmium (10 mg/kg b wt.) and orange peel extract (200 mg/kg b wt.); Group E: orange peel extract (OPE) (200 mg/kg b wt.) and Group F: jamun seed extract (JSE) (200 mg/kg b wt.). Liver biomarkers were estimated on day 7 and day 14. Serum SGOT, SGPT, bilirubin, ALP, and LDH were increased on day 7 and 14 after cadmium treatment. Serum albumin levels decreased on day 7 and day 14. The SGOT, SGPT, bilirubin, ALP, LDH and albumin levels showed a tendency for restoration after treatment with JSE and OPE. There were no alterations in these liver parameters after treatment with OPE and JSE. The results clearly indicate that JSE and OPE were effective in recovering liver biomarkers which were altered by cadmium exposure to rats.

Keywords: Cadmium; Liver biomarkers; Phytochemicals; Orange peel; Jamun seed.

1. INTRODUCTION

Cadmium (Cd) is a heavy metal naturally present in earth crust [1]. Contamination of cadmium spread in the environment through the industrial wastes, agriculture, pesticides, fertilizers, coal, sewage, cigarette smoking and smelting of plastic and rubber products [2]. Cadmium enters into the animal's body including human through the drinking water, respiration, food chain and contact through skin [3]. Cadmium is a well-known harmful substance in nature which affects morphology, physiology and histology of hepatocytes in mammals [4]. Cadmium has also been recognized as a neurotoxic, carcinogenic, hepatotoxic and nephrotoxic heavy metal [5]. Akintunde et al. [6] have reported that cadmium suppressed the antioxidant defense function and also increase the level of reactive oxygen species as well as oxidative stress in mammalian tissues and cells.

Cadmium enters and accumulate into the mammalian hepatic cells and can manifest physiological, morphological, biochemical, inflammation, apoptosis and haemorrhage and cause damage to several cellular organisations [7]. Cadmium has been reported to alter liver biomarkers, degeneration, vacuolization and vascular constriction in liver tissues [3].

Natural antioxidants suppress the effect of cadmium induced toxicities and control the impairments of liver enzymes, cells or tissues which are induced by free radicals and prevent malfunction in hepatic cells [8]. The jamun (*Syzygium cumini*) seed is botanically related to the family Myrtaceae which contains various powerful antioxidants like ellagic acid, flavonoids and phenolic compounds. These phytochemicals neutralize/prevent the effects of free radicals and reduce blood pressure, inflammation in the liver and act as an antidiabetic, antioxidant, anti-bacterial and anti-inflammatory [9]. Jamun seed extract possesses hepatoprotective activity against oxidative damage as a free radical's scavenger and prevents damage in liver tissues or cells [8,9]. Tahir Abbas et al. [10] also reported that the flavonoid contained in jamun pulp extract can repair the hepatic tissues and has hypoglycaemic function.

Orange (sweet orange) peel (*Citrus sinensis*; Rutaceae family) contains several alkaloids such as ascorbic acid, flavonoids, tannins, saponins and hesperidin, and also contains anti-bacterial and anti-inflammatory properties [9,11]. Orange peel extract acts as hepatoprotective against cadmium induced toxicity in Wistar rats [12].

Analysis of hepatic biomarkers such as serum glutamic oxaloacetic transaminase (SGOT), serum glutamic pyruvic transaminase (SGPT), bilirubin (Bil), albumin (Alb), alkaline phosphatases (ALP) and lactate dehydrogenase (LDH) are good indicators to determine liver damage, its severity, pharmacologic source, or the type of hepatotoxicity. Hence, the present study investigated the alternation in liver function parameters such as serum glutamic oxaloacetic transaminase (SGOT), serum glutamic pyruvic transaminase (SGPT), bilirubin (Bil), albumin (Alb), alkaline phosphatases (ALP) and lactate dehydrogenase (LDH) of cadmium exposed Wistar rats. The study also evaluated the possible ameliorative effects of jamun (*Syzygium cumini*) seed and orange (*Citrus sinensis*) peel extracts on liver biomarkers in rats treated with cadmium.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

In this study Wistar rats (*Rattus norvegicus*) (120; 50-60 g; age 2 months) were procured from Asia Scientific Emporium, Varanasi, India and were divided into six groups of 20 rats each. Rats were kept in polypropylene cages under laboratory conditions at room temperature (27-30°C; 12 h dark/light cycle) for 2 weeks acclimatization. They were provided standard food and water *ad libitum*. In this study, the oral doses of cadmium, JSE and OPE were selected near about/in between doses used by previous investigators, Cadmium (5 mg/kg and 10 mg/kg wt. [13]; 8 mg/kg body weight [14]; JSE (200 mg/kg bwt. [9,15]; 250 mg/kg body weight [16]; 5 to 160 mg/kg body weight [17] and OPE (200 mg/kg body weight [9,15]; 250 and 500 mg/kg body weight [18].

2.1. Experimental Design

The rats were treated as Group A - No treatment; Group B - Cadmium; Group C - Cadmium and JSE; Group D - Cadmium and OPE; Group E - OPE; and Group F - JSE. The doses of cadmium (group B, C, D) were 10 mg/kg b wt.; doses of JSE (group C, F) was 200 mg/kg b wt. and doses of OPE (group D, E) was 200 mg/kg b wt. All treatments (at 8:00 a.m.) were orally administered daily to rats with the help of gavages. Preparation of JSE and OPE were performed according to Srivastava et al. [9,15]. Ethical clearance and experimental design was approved by the Research Degree Committee, D.D.U. Gorakhpur University

(RC/FSc/ZOO/2019-20/07/22). The study was conducted in accordance with “Guide for the Care and Use of Laboratory Animals”.

Blood was collected from rats (10 rats from each group after overnight fasting) on day 7 and 14 under light ether anaesthesia. Blood was centrifuged at 3000 rpm for 10 min and sera were separated and stored at -20°C for further analysis. Serum SGOT (serum glutamic oxaloacetic transaminase), SGPT (serum glutamic pyruvic transaminase), bilirubin, albumin, alkaline phosphatases (ALP) and lactate dehydrogenase (LDH) were analysed in duplicate using diagnostic kits (Beacon Diagnostics Private Ltd, India).

2.2. Statistical Analysis

Each data represents mean ± Standard Error (S.E) of six groups. For multiple group comparisons, one way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was used. Differences between groups were tested by Student's t test and Bonferroni post hoc test. The p<0.05 was set for statistical significance.

3. RESULTS

Serum SGOT levels increased after treatment with cadmium (group B) as compared to control (group A) in rats at 7 and 14 days (Figure 1). The cadmium when given to rats in combination with JSE (group C) or OPE (group D) significantly decreased serum SGOT at 7 and 14 days as compared to Group B (cadmium treated). It is clearly evident that extract of JSE and OPE showed protective effect against cadmium exposure to rats. There were no significant changes noticed after treatment with OPE (group E) and JSE (group F) at 7 and 14 days in rats. ANOVA indicates that the treatments were significant (7 day - F=18.134, P< 0.0001; 14 days - F= 147.86, P< 0.0001).

Figure 1. Serum SGOT levels (U/L) of Wistar rats treated either with cadmium, cadmium+jamun seed extract, cadmium+orange peel extract, orange peel extract or jamun seed extract. All values indicate mean ± SE of six specimens.

Figure 2. Serum SGPT levels (U/L) of Wistar rats treated either with cadmium, cadmium+jamun seed extract, cadmium+orange peel extract, orange peel extract or jamun seed extract. All values indicate mean ± SE of six specimens.

Cadmium treatment to rats (group B) provoked an increase in serum SGPT levels on 7 and 14 days (Figure 2) as compared to Group B (cadmium treated). There was a progressive decrease in serum SGPT levels from day 7 to day 14 in Group C (Cd+ JSE) and Group D (Cd+OPE) as compared to Group B (Cd treated) which clearly indicates that JSE and OPE are effective in recovery the SGPT levels which was induced by cadmium (Figure 2). No significant changes were observed after treatment with OPE (group E) and JSE (group F) at 7 and 14 days in rats. ANOVA indicates that the treatments are significant (7 day - $F=19.280, P< 0.0001$; 14 days - $F= 307.99, P< 0.0001$).

Rats treated with cadmium (group B) had decreased serum albumin levels at 7 and 14 days as compared to control (Figure 3). A progressive increase was recorded in serum albumin levels after treatment with cadmium and JSE (group C) or OPE (group D) from 7 to 14 days as compared to group B (cadmium only) which is an indication of hepatoprotective action of JSE and OPE against cadmium toxicity. No significant changes were noticed in rats treated with OPE (group E) and JSE (group F) in rats at 7 and 14 days. ANOVA indicates that the treatments are significant (7 day - $F=11.540, P<0.0001$; 14days - $F=36.897, P<0.0001$).

The bilirubin levels increased progressively in rats after treatment with cadmium (group B) from 7 to 14 days as compared to control (Figure 4). The bilirubin levels were restored to almost near control levels in group C (Cd+ JSE) and group D (Cd+ OPE). These results showed hepatoprotective nature of JSE and OPE against cadmium induced alternation in serum bilirubin levels in rats. In OPE (group E) and JSE (group F) treated rats there was no change in serum bilirubin levels at 7 and 14 days. ANOVA indicates that the treatments are significant (7 day - $F=10.584, P<0.0001$; 14 days - $F=26.357, P<0.0001$).

There was an increase in serum alkaline phosphatase (ALP) levels in rats after treatment with cadmium (group B) at 7 and 14 days as compared to control (group A) (Figure 5). The serum ALP levels decreased from 7 to 14 days as compared to group B when cadmium was administrated with JSE (group C) or OPE (group D).

It clearly indicates hepatoprotective role of JSE and OPE. Rats treated with OPE (group E) and JSE (group F) showed no changes in serum ALP levels at 7 and 14 days. ANOVA indicates that the treatments are significant (7 day - $F=23.525, P<0.0001$; 14 days - $F=119.56, P<0.0001$).

Figure 3. Serum albumin levels (g/100 ml) of Wistar rats treated either with cadmium, cadmium+jamun seed extract, cadmium+orange peel extract, orange peel extract or jamun seed extract. All values indicate mean ± SE of six specimens.

Figure 4. Serum bilirubin levels (mg/100 ml) of Wistar rats treated either with cadmium, cadmium+jamun seed extract, cadmium+orange peel extract, orange peel extract or jamun seed extract. All values indicate mean ± SE of six groups.

Figure 5. Serum ALP levels (mg/100 ml) of Wistar rats treated either with cadmium, cadmium+jamun seed extract, cadmium+orange peel extract, orange peel extract or jamun seed extract. All values indicate mean ± SE of six specimens.

Figure 6. Serum LDH levels (U/L) of Wistar rats treated either with cadmium, cadmium+jamun seed extract, cadmium+orange peel extract, orange peel extract or jamun seed extract. All values indicate mean ± SE of six groups.

Cadmium treatment to rats increased serum lactate dehydrogenase (LDH) levels at 7 and 14 days as compared to Group A (Figure 6). Serum LDH levels showed significant decrease after treatment with cadmium and JSE (group C) or OPE (group D) at 7 and 14 days in rats as compared to group B (only cadmium). The restoration of serum LDH levels in group C and group D is indication of hepatoprotective role of JSE and OPE against cadmium induced liver toxicity. No alternation occurred in serum LDH levels after treatment with OPE (group E) and JSE (group F) in rats. ANOVA indicates that the treatments are significant (7 day - $F=32.369$, $P<0.0001$; 14 days - $F=87.894$, $P<0.0001$).

4. DISCUSSION

There are several heavy metals including cadmium present in environment which are highly hepatotoxic [7]. Cadmium exposure caused severe toxic effects in mammals like nephrotoxicity, neurotoxicity hepatotoxicity, genotoxicity and teratogenicity [2,15]. In this study, JSE and OPE showed protective effects against cadmium induced hepatotoxicity such as serum SGOT, serum SGPT, serum albumin, serum bilirubin, serum alkaline phosphatase and serum lactate dehydrogenase levels in rats. Administration of cadmium significantly increased serum SGOT, SGPT, bilirubin, alkaline phosphatase and lactate dehydrogenase levels and decreased serum albumin levels in rats.

In this study, serum SGOT levels significantly increased after treatment with cadmium. This is in conformity with other reports of increased serum SGOT level in rats was recorded after exposure to toxicants such as lead [19]; carbon tetrachloride [20] and rifampicin [21]. Rat treated with cadmium and jamun seed extract (group C) or orange peel extract (group D) exhibited levels of serum SGOT decreased at 7 day and 14 day which clearly indicates that both JSE and OPE may restore the serum SGOT levels in rat.

Cadmium treatment to rats increased levels of serum SGPT. Other investigators have also reported increased serum SGPT levels in rat after treatment with toxicants carbon tetrachloride [20] and rifampicin [21]. When combined treatment of cadmium with JSE (group C) or OPE (group D) were given to rats, serum SGPT level significantly reduced as compared to Group B. It is clearly evident that JSE and OPE showed hepatoprotective effect against cadmium induced hepatotoxicity in rats.

Increased bilirubin levels were noticed in rats after treatment with cadmium (group B) at 7 and 14 days. The present study derives support from the earlier reports which also describe increased serum bilirubin levels in rats exposure to various toxicants cisplatin [22], malathion [23] and arsenic [24]. When rats were treated with cadmium and jamun seed extract (group C) or orange peel extract (group D) the levels of bilirubin significantly decreased at 7 and 14 days. It confirms that extract of jamun seed and orange peel possess hepatoprotective role against cadmium induced hepatotoxicity in rats.

Decreased serum albumin levels were observed in cadmium treated rats (group B) at 7 and 14 days. Similar results have also been reported by other investigators after treatment with different toxicants aflatoxin and cypermethrin [25], sodium fluoride [26] and aluminum chloride [27]. The combined dose of cadmium and jamun seed extract (group C) or orange peel extract (group D) was effective in restoration of serum albumin to near control levels which is an indication of hepatoprotective action of these extract.

Furthermore, increased serum ALP levels were observed in rats after treatment with cadmium at 7 and 14 days. This is in conformity with the observations of other investigators who have reported increased ALP levels in rats after treatment with various toxicants acetaminophen and thioacetamide [28], arsenic and quinalphos [29], monosodium glutamate [30], deltamethrin [31], fluoride and chlorpyrifos [32]. The hepatoprotective role of JSE and OPE is evident by the observed decrease in serum ALP levels when cadmium

was given in combination with JSE and OPE. Ndubuisi et al. [11] have also noticed similar results when the rats were treated with aqueous extract of zest of *Citrus sinensis* in combination with cadmium.

There was significant increase in serum LDH levels after treatment with cadmium in rats (group B) at 7 and 14 days. Previous studies also observed an increase in serum LDH levels after treatment with toxicants carbofuran [33], lead [34] and endosulfan [35]. Serum LDH levels were progressively decreased after treatment with combined dose of cadmium and JSE or OPE from 7 to 14 day as compared to group B. It depicted hepatoprotective role of JSE and OPE against cadmium induced hepatotoxicity in rats. In past, jamun seed and orange peel extracts have been reported to ameliorate the toxic changes induced by cadmium in kidney biomarkers such as blood urea, uric acid and creatinine of rat [15]. Also protective role of jamun seed and orange peel extracts have been reported for cypermethrin induced nephrotoxicity in rats [12]. Srivastava et al. [9] have reported protective role of jamun seed and orange peel extracts in cypermethrin-induced alterations in serum calcium and phosphate of rats

No significant changes occurred in serum SGOT, SGPT, albumin, bilirubin, alkaline phosphatase and lactate dehydrogenase levels in rats That were treated with JSE and OPE alone. There exists no study regarding the effect of JSE and OPE on liver biomarkers in rats.

5. CONCLUSIONS

The results indicate that cadmium negatively affects the liver biomarkers in rats. Treatment with JSE and OPE were effective in recovering liver biomarkers which were altered by cadmium exposure.

Author Contributions: RPY performed the analysis. RPY and SKS conducted statistical analyses. AKS and NS conceived and designed the experiments. RPY and SKS wrote the manuscript. AKS and NS provided help and advice on draft revisions. All authors read and approved the final version of the manuscript.

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REFERENCES

1. Ufort EP, Uwakwe AA, Essien EB. Oxidative Potentials of Vernonia Calvaona on lipids profile, liver functions and histopathological changes in female albino Wistar rats exposed to iron, cadmium, nickel, lead and cobalt contaminated water. *Curr Res Interdiscip Stud.* 2023; 2(7): 9-32.
2. Yadav RP, Kushwaha VB, Srivastav SK. Toxicity of cadmium and lead in mammal: A brief review. *Int J Zool Investig.* 2023; 9(2): 722-729.
3. Noor KK, Ijaz MU, Ehsan N, Tahir A, Yeni DK, Neamul Kabir, et al. Hepatoprotective role of vitexin against cadmium-induced liver damage in male rats: A biochemical, inflammatory, apoptotic and histopathological investigation. *Biomed Pharmacother.* 2022; 150: 112934.

4. Dardouri K, Haouem S, Gharbi I, Sriha B, Haouas Z, El Hani A, et al. Combined effects of Cd and Hg on liver and kidney histology and function in Wistar rats. *J Agricult Chem Environ*. 2016; 5: 159-169.
5. Sfar M, Souid G, Alminderej FM, Mzoughi Z, El-Ghoul Y, Rihouey C, et al. Structural characterization of polysaccharides from *Coriandrum sativum* Seeds: Hepatoprotective effect against cadmium toxicity in vivo. *Antioxidants*. 2023; 12(2): 455.
6. Akintunde OW, Joseph OO, Afolabi HO, Alamu OA, Abdulrahman A. Protective and ameliorative effects of virgin coconut oil on cadmium-damaged Wistar rats' testes. *World J Surg Surg Res*. 2023; 6: 1440.
7. Deniz GY and Utlu N. Olive leaf extract (*Olea europaea L.*) restores liver functions from cadmium induced liver injury. *J Basic Health*. 2023; 2(1): 8-17.
8. Boulanouar M, Aouacheri O, Saka S. Potential protective effects of turmeric (*curcuma longa*) supplementation on cadmium-induced toxicity in albinos Wistar rat. *Phytothérapie*. 2023; 21(2-3): 137-149.
9. Srivastava BD, Srivastava M, Srivastav SK, Urata M, Suzuki N, Srivastav Ajai K. Cypermethrin-induced alterations in serum calcium and phosphate of rats: protective role of jamun seed and orange peel extracts. *Jordan J Biol Sci*. 2021; 14(3): 417-422.
10. Abbas T, Ahmad KR, Asmatullah, Lone KP, Kanwal MA, Suleman S. Reno-hepatic protective effects of Jambul against chromium induced anomalies in mice. *Punjab Univ J Zool*. 2016; 31(1): 59-67.
11. Ndubuisi A, Ani C, Wenceslaus E, Ugwu-dike, P, Anyaeji P, Ude VC, et al. The effect of aqueous extract of zest of *Citrus sinensis* (AEZCs) on cadmium chloride induced liver toxicity in Wistar rats. *Afr J Biochem Res*. 2020; 14(1): 5-17.
12. Srivastava BD, Srivastava M, Srivastav SK, Urata M, Suzuki N, Srivastav Ajai K. Protective effects of jamun (*Syzygium cumini*) seed and orange (*Citrus sinensis*) peel extracts against cypermethrin induced nephrotoxicity in rats. *Egypt J Basic Clin Pharmacol*. 2021; 11: 101492.
13. Tripathi S, Srivastav Ajai K. Cytoarchitectural alterations in kidney of Wistar rat after oral exposure to cadmium chloride. *Tissue Cell*. 2011; 43(2): 131-136.
14. Clinton EO, Prosper OE, Blessing AA, Jessica EU, Oscar AN, Precious OO, et al. Antioxidant and chelating effects of *Citrus sinensis* peel extract on wistar rats administered with lead and cadmium. *Biol Res*. 2022; 20(3): 1638-1648.
15. Ram Prataap Y, Kushwaha VB, Srivastav Sunil K. Ameliorative effects of jamun seed (*Syzygium cumini*) and orange peel (*Citrus sinensis*) extracts on cadmium induced alterations in blood urea, uric acid and creatinine of rat. *Int J Zool Investig*. 2023; 9(2): 821-829.
16. Sharma B, Siddiqui MS, Kumar SS, Ram G, Chaudhary M. Liver protective effects of aqueous extract of *Syzygium cumini* in Swiss albino mice on alloxan induced diabetes mellitus. *J Pharmaceut Res*. 2013; 6(8): 853-858.
17. Jagetia GC, Manjeshwar SB, Ponemone V. Influence of seed extract of *Syzygium cumini* (Jamun) on mice exposed to different doses of γ -radiation. *J Radiat Res*. 2005; 46(1): 59-65.
18. Ekhtor OC, Osarumwense EP, Akowe AB, Egbe UJ, Aghedo NO, Omozuwa OP, et al. Antioxidant and chelating effects of *Citrus sinensis* peel extract on Wistar rats administered with lead and cadmium. *Biol Res*. 2022; 20(3): 1638-1648.
19. Metwally ESAM, Negm FA, El-din RAS, Nabil EM. Anatomical and histological study of the effect of lead on hepatocytes of albino rats. *Int J Biomed Mater Res*. 2015; 3(4): 34-45.
20. Anandan R, Jayakar B, Karar B, Babuji S, Manavalan R, Kumar RS. Effect of ethanol extract of flowers of *Vitex trifolia* Linn. on CCl₄- induced hepatic injury in rats. *Pakistan J Pharmac Sci*. 2009; 22(4): 391-394.
21. Ifthekar S, Mumtaz M, Nitin M. Evaluation of hepatoprotective and nephroprotective activity of aqueous extract of *Vigna mungo* (Linn.) Hepper on rifampicin-induced toxicity in albino rats. *Int J Health Allied Sci*. 2012; 1(2): 85-91.

22. Aboraya DM, El Baz A, Risha EF, Abdelhamid FM. Hesperidin ameliorates cisplatin induced hepatotoxicity and attenuates oxidative damage, cell apoptosis, and inflammation in rats. *Saudi J Biol Sci.* 2022; 29(5): 3157-3166.
23. Sharma C and Bansal G. Impact of different doses of Malathion on the selected blood parameter in albino rats (*Rattus norvegicus*). *Environ Conserv J.* 2021; 22(1-2): 1-5.
24. Ishaq A, Gulzar H, Hassan A, Kamran M, Riaz M, Parveen A, et al. Ameliorative mechanisms of turmeric-extracted curcumin on arsenic (As)-induced biochemical alterations, oxidative damage, and impaired organ functions in rats. *Environ Sci Pollut Res.* 2021; 28(46): 66313-66326.
25. Hussain S, Khan MZ, Khan A, Javed I, Asi MR. Toxicopathological effects in rats induced by concurrent exposure to aflatoxin and cypermethrin. *Toxicon.* 2009; 53(1): 33-41.
26. Sharma P, Verma PK, Sood S, Singh M, Verma D. Impact of chronic sodium fluoride toxicity on antioxidant capacity, biochemical parameters, and histomorphology in cardiac, hepatic, and renal tissues of Wistar rats. *Biol Trace Elem Res.* 2023; 201(1): 229-241.
27. Obafemi TO, Anyalechi DI, Afolabi BA, Ekundayo BE, Adewale OB, Afolabi OB, et al. Nephroprotective effects of gallic acid and hesperidin in aluminum chloride-induced toxicity in rats. *Phytomed Plus.* 2022; 2(4): 100378.
28. Jain NK, Singhai AK. Protective effects of *Phyllanthus acidus* (L.) Skeels leaf extracts on acetaminophen and thioacetamide induced hepatic injuries in Wistar rats. *Asian Pac J Trop Med.* 2011; 4(6): 470-474.
29. Verma PK, Singh P, Sharma P, Sood S, Raina R. Dose-dependent oxidative damage in erythrocytes and hepatic tissue of wistar rats concurrently exposed with arsenic and quinalphos: a subacute study. *Biol Trace Elem Res.* 2022; 200(5): 2160-2173.
30. Abd-Elkareem M, Soliman M, El-Rahman MAMA, Nasser S, Khalil A. The protective effect of *Nigella sativa* seeds against monosodium glutamate-induced hepatic dysfunction in rats. *Toxicol Rep.* 2022; 9: 147-153.
31. Abdel-Daim MM, Abuzead SM, Halawa SM. Protective role of *Spirulina platensis* against acute deltamethrin-induced toxicity in rats. *PLoS One.* 2013; 9(8): e72991.
32. Raina R, Baba NA, Verma PK, Sultana M, Singh M. Hepatotoxicity induced by subchronic exposure of fluoride and chlorpyrifos in Wistar rats: mitigating effect of ascorbic acid. *Biol Trace Elem Res.* 2015; 166(2): 157-162.
33. Jaiswal SK, Siddiqi NJ, Sharma B. Studies on the ameliorative effect of curcumin on carbofuran induced perturbations in the activity of lactate dehydrogenase in Wistar rats. *Saudi J Biol Sci.* 2018; 25(8): 1585-1592.
34. Alwaleedi SA. Hematobiochemical changes induced by lead intoxication in male and female albino mice. *Nat J Physiol Pharmacy Pharmacol.* 2016; 6(1): 46-51.
35. Manokaran K, Rao VK, Manjula N, Rao SD, Kumar SP. The effect of vitamin C on Endosulfan-induced oxidative stress parameters in prepubertal rats. *Biomedicines.* 2019; 39(2): 333-338.